

Latest Cross-Section Measurements from T2K with the ND280 Detector

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on behalf of the T2K Collaboration

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- Precision oscillation measurements require accurate modelling of neutrino-nucleus interactions.
- Our understanding of neutrino-nucleus interactions remains incomplete:

What interaction really occurs?

What role do nuclear effects play?

How does interaction modelling bias E_ν ?

- T2K provides leading constraints on neutrino interactions through:
 - Exclusive final-state measurements at ND280
 - Detectors with multiple target nucleons (C, O, H₂O)
 - Use of topological and TKI-based observables

$$N \approx \underbrace{\Phi(E_\nu)}_{\text{Beam flux}} \otimes \underbrace{\sigma(k, k')}_{\nu\text{-}A \text{ cross section}} \otimes \underbrace{\epsilon}_{\text{Signal efficiency}} \otimes \underbrace{P(\nu_\alpha \rightarrow \nu_\beta)}_{\text{Oscillation probability}}$$

Super-Kamiokande

Far detector (FD)

ν_μ, ν_e

$L / E \sim 295 \text{ km} / 0.6 \text{ GeV}$

$$N_{\text{ND}} \approx \Phi_{\text{ND}}(E_\nu) \otimes \sigma(k, k') \otimes \epsilon_{\text{ND}}$$

ND280

Near detector (ND)

ν_μ

Detectors need to measure neutrino beam at two positions, fixing L / E

~96% pure ν_μ beam passes through ND

Measured as mix of ν_μ and ν_e at FD

Fit expected appearance spectra with ND inputs

Precise knowledge of **cross sections** essential

- T2K uses complementary near detectors to control interaction systematics across final states and nuclear targets.

ND280 (2.5° off-axis, $E_\nu \sim 0.6$ GeV)

- Fine-Grained Detectors: main target masses
 - Time Projection Chambers: reconstruct particle tracks
- Used for new $\nu_e CC \pi^+$, $NC 1 \pi^+$, $\nu_\mu CC 0 \pi N p$ measurements

WAGASCI-BabyMIND (1.5° off-axis, $E_\nu \sim 0.7$ GeV)

- 3D grid scintillator structure
 - 4π angular coverage
- Used for new $\nu_\mu CC 0 \pi$ measurement

Interaction

Leptonic side

Graphic courtesy of Katharina Lachner

Hadronic side

Interaction

Leptonic side

Graphic courtesy of Katharina Lachner

Hadronic side

CCQE dominant at T2K up to ~ 1.1 GeV
RES/DIS increasingly present above this

Graphic courtesy of Katharina Lachner

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Neutrino Interactions at T2K > Measurement History

- First measurement of $\nu_e A \rightarrow e^- \pi^+ X$ on carbon [recently published in PRL](#).
- This channel:
 - Contributes $\sim 10\%$ to the ν_e appearance (on H_2O) at far detector
 - Constrains models of pion production and nuclear final-state interactions
- Novel reconstruction for trackless pions which decay to Michel electrons.
- Very low statistics, π^0/γ backgrounds dominate.

$0.35 < p_e < 30 \text{ GeV}/c, \quad \cos\theta_e > 0.7, \quad p_\pi < 1.5 \text{ GeV}/c$

TPC sample: fully reconstructed pion tracks

e^-
 π^+
 μ^+
 e^+

FGD sample: pions below tracking threshold, p_π reconstructed from Michel electron hits

Plots from Phys. Rev. Lett. **135**, 151802 (2025)

- Three-dimensional fit in outgoing final-state particle kinematics (p_e, θ_e, p_π):

Plots from Phys. Rev. Lett. **135**, 151802 (2025)

- Reveals significant model tension in ν_e pion production at T2K energies.
- Cross sections over-predicted by generators; $\sim 3\sigma$ **discrepancy in $0.45 < p_\pi < 1.5 \text{ GeV/c}$ region.**
- Uncertainties statistically dominated; more data and better $e-\gamma$ separation needed for higher precision.

Uncertainty source	Fractional error on σ [%]
Detector response	5.7
Flux model	6.8
Interaction and background modelling	7.8
Target mass	0.7
Total statistical	20.6
Total systematic	11.7

- First differential measurement of $\nu_\ell p(n) \rightarrow \nu_\ell n(p)\pi^\pm$ on carbon [recently published in PRL](#) and [selection published in PRD](#).
- Significant background to ν_e appearance due to π^+ misidentification.
- Low statistics, lack of outgoing lepton and strong final-state interaction dependence make this measurement particularly challenging.

$$0.2 < p_\pi < 1.0 \text{ GeV}/c, \quad \cos \theta_\pi > 0.5$$

Plots from Phys. Rev. D **112**, 072008 (2025)

- Differential results in outgoing final-state charged pion kinematics; larger bin indices within same angular region are ordered with increasing momentum:

Plots from Phys. Rev. Lett. **135**, 171803 (2025)

- Event generators under-predict total flux-integrated cross section by $\sim 30\%$, but uncertainties large.
- This channel remains poorly constrained experimentally despite its oscillation relevance.
- Comparisons with different final-state interactions models reveals substantial variation between models.

- First measurement of $\nu_\mu A \rightarrow \mu^- A'$ using WAGASCI-BabyMIND; [published in PRD 3 days ago!](#)
- 3D grid scintillator structure of WAGASCI allows tagging of high-angle tracks.
- Event rates counted simultaneously at WAGASCI (H₂O target) and proton module (CH target):

$$p_\mu > 0.3 \text{ GeV}/c, \quad \cos \theta_\mu > 0.34$$

Plots from Phys. Rev. D **112**, 112020 (2026)

- Simultaneous fit on H₂O and CH targets from different detectors (p_μ, θ_μ):

Plots from Phys. Rev. D **112**, 112020 (2026)

- Results compatible with event generators.
- Provides important validation of interaction models on matching target with Super-Kamiokande.

- Updated measurement from [previous publication](#) with additional statistics and oxygen target.
- Measures CCQE-like interactions with N protons.
- Transverse kinematic imbalance (TKI) observables, $\delta p_T - \delta \alpha_T$ and $p_N - \cos \theta_\mu$, directly probe nuclear effects while minimising neutrino energy reconstruction bias (see [Phys. Rev. C 94, 015503](#) for more on TKI variables).

$0.525 < p_p < 1.1 \text{ GeV}/c$, $\cos \theta_p > 0.3$, $0.225 < p_\mu < 10 \text{ GeV}/c$, $\cos \theta_\mu > -0.6$

$$\delta \vec{p}_T \equiv \vec{p}_T^{\ell'} + \vec{p}_T^{N'}$$

$$\delta \alpha_T \equiv \arccos \frac{-\vec{p}_T^{\ell'} \cdot \delta \vec{p}_T}{p_T^{\ell'} \delta p_T}$$

- Results projected along distributions of TKI observables:

- Data prefers Neut cascade model to describe final-state interactions.
- Low post-fit p value indicates limitations in the fit model, possibly due to limited background freedom.

- π^0 detector was replaced with new upstream modules in 2023:

- Four new results including several world first measurements:
 - $\nu_e CC\pi^+$ on C using ND280
 - $NC1\pi^+$ on C using ND280
 - $\nu_\mu CC0\pi$ on CH/H₂O using WAGASCI-BabyMIND
 - $\nu_\mu CC0\pi Np$ on C and O with TKI variables using ND280
- Many other results in the analysis pipeline and an exciting future ahead with the upgraded near detector.

